

A Structural Equation Model of Risk Factors for Work-related Musculoskeletal Disorders in Manufacturing: A Systems Approach

Mohammad Khandan, Seyed Abolfazl Zakerian, Shahin Akhondzadeh, Mansour Shamsipour, Majid Nili Ahmadabadi

¹ School of Public Health, Tehran University of Medical Sciences, Tehran, Iran. ORCID: 0000-0001-7883-8389; ² School of Public Health, Tehran University of Medical Sciences, ORCID: 0000-0001-5172-9318, Corresponding author: Email: zakerian@tums.ac.ir; ³ Roozbeh Hospital, Tehran University of Medical Sciences. ORCID: 0000-0002-2277-5101; ⁴ Institute for Environmental Research, Tehran University of Medical Sciences, ORCID: 0000-0002-8037-1447; ⁵ Department of Management, University of Qom, Qom, Iran. ORCID: 0000-0002-3872-2397.

Abstract: Abstract: Work-related musculoskeletal disorders (WRMSDs) represent a significant occupational issue globally, particularly among production manufacturing workers. This study aims to identify and analyze the risk factors contributing to WRMSDs using a systems approach and Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) in manufacturing companies in Qom Province, Iran. A cross-sectional study was conducted in 2024 among 393 employees selected via stratified random sampling. Data were gathered through self-reported questionnaires, including individual and behavioral, Depression, Anxiety, Stress Scale-21, and Nordic Musculoskeletal Questionnaires, alongside Ergonomics Checkpoints and documented workplace measures. Results indicated a high WRMSDs prevalence (76.8%), with the lower back (42.5%) and knees (35.6%) most affected. SEM analysis revealed that workplace environmental factors (e.g., noise, vibration) and behavioral factors (e.g., sleep quantity, physical activity) significantly contribute to WRMSDs, both directly and indirectly via psychological mediators. Individual factors, such as age and work experience, showed direct associations with WRMSDs, while job-related factors had limited impact. Psychological factors emerged as both direct contributors and key mediators. These findings underscore the multifactorial nature of WRMSDs and the necessity for integrated interventions addressing workplace conditions and psychological well-being. This systems-based approach highlights effective strategies for mitigating WRMSDs in manufacturing settings.

Keywords: Work-related Musculoskeletal Disorder, Manufacturing, Systems Approach, Structural Equation Model.

Um modelo de equações estruturais de fatores de risco para distúrbios musculoesqueléticos relacionados ao trabalho na indústria: uma abordagem sistêmica

Resumo: Os distúrbios musculoesqueléticos relacionados ao trabalho (DMRT) representam um problema ocupacional significativo em escala global, com especial relevância entre trabalhadores da indústria de manufatura de produção. Este estudo objetiva identificar e analisar os fatores de risco que contribuem para os DMRT, empregando uma abordagem sistêmica e Modelagem de Equações Estruturais (MEE) em empresas de manufatura na província de Qom, Irão. Um estudo transversal foi conduzido em 2024 com 393 funcionários selecionados por amostragem aleatória estratificada. Os dados foram coletados por meio de questionários autoadministrados, incluindo fatores individuais e comportamentais, a Escala de Depressão, Ansiedade e Stresse-21 e o Questionário Nórdico de Sintomas Musculoesqueléticos, complementados por Pontos de Verificação Ergonômica e medidas documentadas do ambiente laboral. Os resultados indicaram uma elevada prevalência de DMRT (76,8%), sendo a região lombar (42,5%) e os joelhos (35,6%) as áreas mais afetadas. A análise por MEE revelou que fatores ambientais do local de trabalho (e.g., ruído, vibração) e fatores comportamentais (e.g., quantidade de sono, atividade física) contribuem significativamente para os DMRT, tanto de forma direta quanto indireta, por meio de mediadores psicológicos. Fatores individuais, como idade e experiência laboral, apresentaram associações diretas com os DMRT, enquanto fatores relacionados ao trabalho demonstraram impacto limitado. Os fatores psicológicos destacaram-se como contribuidores diretos e mediadores-chave. Esses achados reforçam a natureza multifatorial dos DMRT e a necessidade de intervenções integradas que abordem as condições do ambiente de trabalho e o bem-estar psicológico. Esta abordagem baseada em sistemas destaca estratégias eficazes para a mitigação dos DMRT em contextos de manufatura.

Palavras-chave: Transtorno Musculoesquelético Relacionado ao Trabalho, Manufatura, Abordagem Sistêmica, Modelo de Equações Estruturais.

1. Introduction

Work-related musculoskeletal disorders (WRMSDs) represent a significant global occupational health issue, affecting millions of workers and imposing considerable economic burdens on various industries. In 2019, WRMSDs impacted approximately 1.71 billion individuals around the world, contributing to 149 million years lived with disability (Cieza et al., 2020). These disorders are the leading cause of work-related disabilities, resulting in important challenges for industries (Demissie et al., 2024). For example, in Germany, WRMSDs resulted in production losses amounting to EUR 17.2 billion and a loss of gross value added totaling EUR 30.4 billion in 2016, with the manufacturing sector experiencing the most significant economic impact (European Agency for Safety and Health at Work. et al., 2019). In Iran, the prevalence of WRMSDs is similarly concerning; however, local data regarding their specific risk factors and impacts is limited (Parno et al., 2017).

Despite technological advancements, many production tasks in manufacturing industries remain human-centric, exposing workers to musculoskeletal risks such as heavy manual handling and poorly designed workstations, with worker capabilities playing a more critical role than machinery (Katiraei et al., 2021). These conditions contribute to a high incidence of WRMSDs, which not only put worker health at risk but also result in prolonged absenteeism. Median recovery times range from 12 days in the United States (Bureau of Labor Statistics, 2016) to six weeks for severe cases in Australia (Oakman et al., 2019). The associated financial costs, including direct medical expenses and indirect productivity losses, highlight the urgency of addressing WRMSDs, particularly in the manufacturing sector, where human labor remains essential.

While the global burden of WRMSDs is well-documented, significant research gaps remain, particularly in understanding how individual, occupational, and environmental factors interact to contribute to these disorders in specific contexts, such as Iran's production sector. Existing studies often concentrate on isolated risk factors, leaving the complex interplay of physical, psychological, and workplace elements insufficiently explored. Furthermore, the limited studies that have considered various factors typically gathered data subjectively through self-reporting methods, even regarding environmental factors like vibration (Dong et al., 2021; Kar et al., 2023a). In contrast, employing objective methods to collect data on these factors would yield more reliable results. This gap impedes the development of targeted prevention strategies tailored to the specific needs of the local workforce. To address this issue, research employing advanced analytical methods, such as Structural Equation Modeling (SEM), is needed to model these multifaceted relationships and inform effective interventions (Tripathy et al., 2018).

This study examines the risk factors for WRMSDs among employees in production manufacturing enterprises in Qom Province, Iran. SEM was used to identify the main environmental factors (such as noise and lighting), job-related factors (such as workstation design), and individual factors (such as age and gender) that contribute to WRMSDs. Additionally, the interaction of these factors and their collective influence on the occurrence of WRMSDs was evaluated, providing decision-makers with evidence-based insights to develop effective preventive measures. This research addresses the need for specialized data in regions and countries like Iran, where manufacturing plays a vital role in the economy, yet comprehensive investigations into WRMSDs are limited. By elucidating these factors, the study aims to enable safer and more productive workplaces in the region, ultimately enhancing worker well-being.

2. Literature Review

Work-related musculoskeletal disorders pose a significant challenge to occupational health, arising from a complex interplay of individual, occupational, and environmental risk factors. These disorders impact employees across various industries, with production and manufacturing workers being particularly vulnerable due to the physical demands of their roles (Choobineh et al., 2016). A systematic review by Parno et al. (2017) reported a wide prevalence of WRMSDs in Iran, ranging from 20% to 80% depending on the industry and contributing factors studied, highlighting the need for context-specific research. The significant burden of WRMSDs (Cieza et al., 2020) highlights the necessity of understanding the complex etiology of WRMSDs to develop effective prevention strategies.

Research has identified numerous risk factors associated with WRMSDs. Physical workplace factors are well-documented contributors (Katiraei et al., 2021; Talapatra et al., 2024). Choobineh et al. (2016) found that awkward postures and repetitive motions significantly increase the prevalence of musculoskeletal symptoms among industrial workers. Similarly, another study emphasized the role of inappropriate tools and ergonomic deficiencies in exacerbating WRMSDs among workers (Soares et al., 2019). In addition to physical factors, psychosocial risks, including job stress and low job control, have been shown to increase musculoskeletal pain (Fan et al., 2024; Jensen et al., 2002; Kar et al., 2023b; Russo et al., 2020). Krishnan et al. (2021) further noted that personal factors, such as age, lack of exercise, and smoking, interact with occupational hazards to raise WRMSD risk, suggesting a multifactorial framework.

Although musculoskeletal pain is influenced by a variety of risk factors that affect multiple body parts rather than a single area (Leite et al., 2021), limited research has explored the interplay between these diverse risk factors and the onset of upper and lower limb WRMSDs. In addition, the interplay among these diverse risk factors remains underexplored, suggesting that isolated analyses may overlook critical interactions. For example, Nascimento et al. (2024) found that psychological stress mediates the relationship between other factors and WRMSDs, yet few studies integrate individual, behavioral, occupational, and environmental dimensions into a cohesive model. This gap is particularly pronounced in manufacturing settings, where human-centered tasks address this complexity, and advanced analytical methods such as SEM can yield significant benefits. SEM enables researchers to model latent variables, such as perceived stress or ergonomic quality, which cannot be directly observed. This approach reduces measurement error compared to traditional statistical methods (Christ et al., 2014; Dong et al., 2021). Tripathy et al. (2018) demonstrated the utility of SEM in elucidating the relationships between workplace ergonomics, worker health, and productivity, offering a more comprehensive perspective than traditional methods such as correlation or regression. Nascimento et al. (2024) further argued that SEM's capacity to test multiple pathways simultaneously makes it particularly effective for identifying risk factors associated with WRMSDs, especially in multifactorial contexts. For instance, Dong et al. (2021) employed SEM to provide a deeper explanation for the relationship between work-related factors and Low Back Pain (LBP), a finding that was missed using traditional analyses using logistic regression.

While these studies highlight SEM's advantages, gaps persist in its application to WRMSDs within specific regional contexts, such as the production industries in Iran. Lee et al. (2023) emphasized the necessity for localized research to tailor protective systems to

the unique characteristics of the workforce, noting that variations in risk exposure exist across different countries. In Iran, despite a high prevalence of WRMSDs (Parno et al., 2017), there have been limited studies utilizing SEM to investigate how risk factors - such as workstation design, psychological stress, and personal habits - interact to impact workers' upper and lower limbs. This lack of integrated, context-specific data hinders the development of effective interventions for manufacturing workers.

By synthesizing previous findings on physical, psychosocial, and personal risk factors (Choobineh et al., 2016; Fan et al., 2024; Russo et al., 2020) and leveraging the analytical strengths of SEM (Nascimento et al., 2024; Tripathy et al., 2018), this study addresses the need for a comprehensive and localized understanding of the etiology of WRMSDs. The resulting insights aim to bridge existing research gaps and guide the design of multidisciplinary prevention strategies.

3. Methods

3.1. Study design

This cross-sectional study was conducted on employees working in six companies in 2024. The study focuses on various manufacturing industries. These industries, including chemicals, textiles, food processing, and automotive parts production, represent a diverse range of manufacturing environments. This diversity ensures a comprehensive analysis of WRMSDs across various workplace conditions.

3.2. Participants

Employees from accessible companies were selected using stratified random sampling and included in the study. Each manufacturing company was considered a stratum, and samples were allocated proportionally to each company. Finally, simple random sampling was utilized to select the employees within the strata. Participants included production line workers, machine operators, quality control inspectors, maintenance staff, and office personnel. This diverse representation of job roles allows for a thorough investigation of the risk factors associated with WRMSDs in different occupational settings.

The total population (universe) of workers employed across the six companies was approximately 850. Based on the Krejcie and Morgan (1970) table, a minimum of 265 participants is recommended to determine sample size. Additionally, considering the requirements for SEM used in this study, the minimum sample size was calculated as 385 participants, based on the used equation. This number was obtained given a confidence level of 95% ($\alpha=0.05$, and the critical value=1.96), considering the worst case ($p=q=0.5$), and assuming a margin of error (MOE) of 5%, the minimum sample size consisted of 385 responses (n) through the equation presented in Figure 1.

$$n = \frac{(z_{\alpha})^2 (p)(q)}{MOE^2}$$

Figure 1. Equation for calculating the minimum number of samples for SEM

With 393 employees participating in the study, the sample size exceeds both the Krejcie and Morgan threshold and the SEM requirement (Hair et al., 2021), ensuring an adequate number of participants for robust statistical analysis.

3.3. Instruments

Study data were collected through self-reporting methods after providing necessary explanations about the importance of the topic and ensuring full adherence to ethical research guidelines using standard questionnaires.

- Individual, behavioral/habitual, and occupational information questionnaire: Using this questionnaire, demographic information of participants including age, gender, level of education, work experience, Body Mass Index (BMI), marital status, occupied in a second job, and behavioral/habitual factors such as duration of daily physical activity (in minutes), sleep quantity during 24 hours (in hours), and smoking, along with some job-related factors were collected. Job role, job demand (physically dominant, mentally dominant), and shift working (yes, no) were also inquired. Job type was derived from job role and categorized into two groups of administrative or operational.

- Depression Anxiety and Stress Scale-21 (DASS-21): This questionnaire was used to assess psychological factors and consisted of 21 questions with three subscales of seven questions each to assess the states of stress, anxiety, and depression. Participants responded to 21 questions related to their symptoms of stress, anxiety, and depression using a four-point Likert scale from 0 to 3, corresponding to never, sometimes, often, and almost always, respectively (Babazadeh et al., 2016); for better comparison and analysis against the 42 questions version, the score was multiplied by 2. The higher the score, the more severe the individual's stress, anxiety, and depression (Asghari et al., 2008). The validity and reliability of the Persian version of the questionnaire have been previously confirmed (Kakemam et al., 2022).

- Ergonomic Checkpoints: this tool was presented by the International Labour Organization (ILO) in collaboration with the International Ergonomics Association (IEA), and provides simple and low-cost solutions to improve work conditions. Because it is a good guide for improving the workplace, it can be an effective instrument for detecting and assessing work-related risk factors by taking into account the risk score for each item (Ahmadi et al., 2017). Workstation design (13 checkpoints), tools (14 checkpoints), and materials handling (17 checkpoints) sections of the Persian version (Dastranj & Helali, 2015) with no (the measure has already been taken properly or is not needed, 1) and yes (the measure would be worthwhile, 0) as choices for each checkpoint.

- Environmental factors: Exposure to these factors (lighting, vibration, temperature, and humidity) was determined using the documentation and measurement results available in each industry. For participants who were exposed to these agents, the results were classified as acceptable or unacceptable based on Iran's Occupational Exposure Limits (OEL) (Environmental and Occupational Health Center of Iran (EOHCI), 2021).

- Nordic Musculoskeletal Questionnaire (NMQ): WRMSDs were assessed using the NMQ (Kuorinka et al., 1987), a self-reported questionnaire that assesses the prevalence of musculoskeletal symptoms in nine areas of the body: neck, shoulders, elbows, wrists and hands, hips, knees, lower back, upper back, and ankles and feet. The validity and reliability of its Persian version have been proven (Choobineh et al., 2004). The severity of WRMSDs was checked using a four-level answer including no pain (scale 0), mild pain (scale 1), moderate pain (scale 2), and severe pain (scale 3) (Ramdan et al., 2019). Respondents who reported any level of pain in the mentioned parts of the body in the past 12 months were considered to have a WRMSDs.

The inclusion criteria were people who volunteered to participate in this survey and were older than 18 and with more than one year of working experience. Pregnant women

and people with musculoskeletal diseases caused by non-work-related factors, like trauma, malignant tumors and infectious diseases were excluded.

Before starting the questionnaire, all participants were provided with an information letter that outlined the details of the informed consent. The current study has been approved by the Ethical Board at Tehran University of Medical Sciences (approval ID: IR.TUMS.SPH.REC.1402.262).

3.4. Data analysis

Mean, standard deviation (SD), frequency, and percentage were used for data description. Univariate relationships between outcome (WRMSDs) and studied factors were examined using the Mann-Whitney U test (for continuous variables) or chi-square (for categorical variables) using SPSS V24. In addition, the relationship between the visible and latent variables was analyzed using SEM. The partial least-square (PLS) estimation approach produced the SEM model's parameter estimate through SmartPLS 4. Various fit indices assessed the SEM model's Goodness of Fit (GoF): Chi-square/df, Goodness of Fit Index (GFI), Adjusted Goodness-of-Fit Index (AGFI), Comparative Fit Index (CFI), Tucker Lewis Index (TLI), Normed Fit Index (NFI), Parsimony Goodness of Fit Index (PGFI), Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR), and Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA). The SEM was considered to have an acceptable fit if the Chi-square/df is less than 3 (Yildiz & Ülker, 2017), the RMSEA is less than 0.08 (Yildiz & Ülker, 2017), AGFI index as low as 0.80 (Brett & Drasgow, 2002), PGFI value of 0.5 or greater (Jöreskog & Soerbom, 1996), GFI between 0 and 1 (Belay et al., 2024) and other fit indices are greater than 0.90 (Yildiz & Ülker, 2017). P-values equal to or less than 0.05 were considered statistically significant. For incremental fit indices (NFI, TLI, CFI), values equal to or greater than 0.90 are conventionally preferred (Hair, 2010). However, in exploratory studies involving complex constructs, values in the range of 0.70 to 0.80 may be considered acceptable when supported by other robust fit indices (Marsh et al., 2004).

Additionally, various criteria were employed to evaluate the reliability and validity of the constructs examined in the study. These included Cronbach's alpha and composite reliability, which is further divided into two types: ρ_a (rho_a) and ρ_c (rho_c). The Average Variance Extracted (AVE) was also utilized to indicate the proportion of variance in the items that is attributable to the construct versus measurement error. AVE values of 0.5 or higher are considered the minimum acceptable threshold for construct validity, indicating that the construct explains at least half of the variance in the items.

The Fornell-Larcker criterion was also applied, one of the most commonly used methods for assessing discriminant validity in SEM. According to this criterion, the square root of the AVE for each construct should be greater than the highest correlation of that construct with any other construct.

4. Results

4.1. Individual factors

In total, 393 people out of 410, with a response rate equal to 95.85%, participated in the study, and 322 (81.9%) were male. The average age was 35.93 ± 7.90 years, ranging from 18 to 59. Most individuals had a diploma in education (43.3%). Table 1 presents the participants' general characteristics.

Table 1. Description of studied variables and their association with WRMSDs (n=393)

Factor	Variable	Characteristic	Mean ± SD or N(%)	WRMSDs N(%)	P
Individual	Gender	Female	71(18.1)	59(83.1)	0.17
		Male	322(81.9)	243(75.46)	
	Marital status	Single	85(21.6)	62(72.9)	0.63
		Married	299(76.1)	233(77.9)	
		Divorced-Widow	9(2.3)	7(77.8)	
	Education level	Lower Diploma	116(29.5)	91(78.4)	0.37
		Diploma	170(43.3)	134(78.8)	
		Higher Diploma	107(27.2)	77(72.0)	
	Second job	No	336(85.5)	256(76.2)	0.46
	Yes	57(14.5)	46(80.7)		
Age (year)		35.93 ± 7.90	-	0.02	
Work experience (year)		6.26 ± 5.47	-	0.01	
BMI (kg/m ²)		26.18 ± 3.94	-	0.42	
Behavioral/Habitual	Smoking	No	299(76.1)	225(75.2)	0.18
	Yes	94(23.9)	77(81.9)		
	Physical activity (hrs./day)		22.0 ± 31.89	-	<0.001
	Sleep Quantity (hrs./day)		6.58 ± 1.21	-	0.005
Psychological	Stress		15.88 ± 9.40	-	<0.001
	Anxiety		7.61 ± 6.82	-	<0.001
	Depression		9.77 ± 8.49	-	<0.001
Job-related	Workstation design	Tools	9.43 ± 2.17	-	0.05
			10.34 ± 2.74	-	0.35
	Shift working	No	318(80.9)	243(76.4)	0.68
		Yes	75(19.1)	59(78.7)	
	Job type	Operational	317(80.7)	246(77.6)	0.47
		Administrative	76(19.3)	56(73.7)	
	Job demand	Physical	260(66.2)	207(79.6)	<0.001
		Mental	133(33.8)	95(71.4)	
	Manual material handling	NA	152(38.7)	114(75.0)	0.38
		Yes_Acceptable	160(40.7)	123(76.9)	
Yes_Unacceptable		81(20.6)	65(80.2)		
Work environmental	Noise	NA	128(32.6)	95(74.2)	0.04
		Yes_Acceptable	115(29.3)	81(70.4)	
		Yes_Unacceptable	150(38.2)	126(84.0)	
	Vibration	NA	264(67.2)	203(76.9)	0.11
		Yes_Acceptable	92(23.4)	66(71.7)	
		Yes_Unacceptable	37(9.4)	33(89.2)	
Lightning	Acceptable	362(92.1)	279(77.1)	0.72	
	Unacceptable	31(7.9)	23(74.2)		
Temperature	Acceptable	342(87.0)	261(76.3)	0.52	
	Unacceptable	51(13.0)	41(80.4)		
Humidity	Acceptable	351(89.3)	269(76.6)	0.88	
	Unacceptable	42(10.7)	33(78.6)		

Notes. SD: Standard Deviation; WRMSDs: Work-Related Musculoskeletal Disorders at least in one part of the body in the past year; NA: Not Applicable; BMI: Body Mass Index; P: P-values for the chi-square or Mann-Whitney U tests. Values significant at $P \leq 0.05$, and $P \leq 0.001$.

4.2. Psychological factors

The mean and SD of all three factors, stress, anxiety, and depression, are shown in Table 1. In addition, the differences between the two groups with and without WRMSDs were significant ($P < 0.01$). The reliability of the applied questionnaires was assessed using Cronbach's alpha coefficient and was measured as 0.80, 0.73, and 0.77, for stress, anxiety, and depression, respectively.

4.3. Work environmental factors

The conditions of exposure to the five environmental factors of work (noise, vibration, lighting, temperature, and humidity) are shown in Table 1. It was checked whether

exposure to them was acceptable or unacceptable, while the factor was in the work environment. Noise and vibration were not applicable (NA) in all cases. Acceptable condition means that despite the factor being presented in the workplace, it was acceptable or workers wore personal protective equipment (PPE) and their exposure was under control in this way. The noise was in the worst situation compared to the other studied factors, with 38.2% unacceptable exposure. Furthermore, there were significant differences between the WRMSDs groups ($P < 0.05$).

4.4. Job-related factors

Regarding their job, the majority were production line workers (80.7%), in non-managerial situations (90.3%), and with physical as the dominant demand (66.2%). Most participants were not in shift-working system (80.9%). Workstation design and tools were continuous variables; their mean and SD were 9.43 ± 2.17 and 10.34 ± 2.74 respectively. Workstation design was associated with WRMSDs ($P \leq 0.05$), while the other one was not ($P > 0.05$). Among other factors, job demands caused a significant difference in WRMSDs prevalence as well ($P < 0.05$).

4.5. Prevalence of the WRMSDs

Overall, 302 (76.8%) of participants reported WRMSDs symptoms in at least one of the body regions within the past 12 months. Musculoskeletal disorder symptoms were most commonly reported in the lower back (42.5%), followed by the knees (35.6%). The least common parts reported were the elbows (8.4%) and tights (10.2%). Severe, moderate, and mild pain were dominant in the knees (4.8%), lower back (13.2%), and knees (22.9%), respectively. The incidence of WRMSDs among the studied individuals is shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Prevalence of WRMSDs symptoms and pain severity among participants (n=393)

Body part	WRMSDs* N (%)	Severity of pain			
		No	Mild	Moderate	Severe
Neck	129(32.8)	264(67.2)	99(25.2)	21(5.3)	9(2.3)
Shoulders	101(25.7)	292(74.3)	73(18.6)	18(4.6)	10(2.5)
Upper back	99(25.2)	294(74.8)	73(18.6)	22(5.6)	4(1.0)
Lower back	167(42.5)	226(57.5)	107(27.2)	52(13.2)	8(2.0)
Elbows	33(8.4)	360(91.6)	22(5.6)	3(0.8)	8(2.0)
Wrists	64(16.3)	329(83.7)	40(10.2)	16(4.1)	8(2.0)
Tights	40(10.2)	353(89.8)	31(7.9)	8(2.0)	1(0.3)
Knees	140(35.6)	253(64.4)	90(22.9)	31(7.9)	19(4.8)
Feet/Ankles	56(14.2)	337(85.8)	37(9.4)	11(2.8)	8(2.0)

* Work-related musculoskeletal disorder at least in one part of the body in the past year

4.6. Risk Factors for WRMSDs

To identify risk factors for musculoskeletal disorders, a model was developed comprising five independent latent variables, including job-related factors, behavioral/habitual factors, workplace-related factors, psychological factors, and individual factors, and a dependent latent variable (musculoskeletal disorders). Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) was employed using the Partial Least Squares (PLS) approach. Based on the fit indices, the measurement model initially demonstrated poor to moderate fit. To improve the model, the 'smoking' variable was removed from the observed variables of the

behavioral/habituallatent factor, and the model was re-evaluated. Figure 2 illustrates the revised model structure.

Mohammad Khandan, Seyed Abolfazl Zakerian, et al.

Figure 2. The final model structure

Notes, WRMSDs: Work-Related Musculoskeletal Disorders, BMI: Body Mass Index, WE: Work Experience, PhAD: Physical Activity Duration, SQ: Sleep Quantity, MH: Manual Handling, WorkstationD: Workstation Design.

GoF indices for the revised model indicated that the Chi-square/df value was 2.478, reflecting an acceptable model fit. The RMSEA value of 0.06 demonstrated improvement compared to the first model. The PGFI and AGFI indices, with values of 0.74 and 0.81, respectively, suggest a reasonable balance between model fit and complexity. The GFI

A Structural Equation Model of Risk Factors for Work-related Musculoskeletal Disorders in Manufacturing

was 0.84, indicating an adequate fit. The SRMR index, at 0.05, was desirable. The fit indices of NFI (0.744), TLI (0.764), and CFI (0.713) were below the conventional threshold of 0.90; however, they demonstrated substantial improvement compared to the initial model. Although these values fall short of the ideal cut-off point of 0.90, they align with acceptable ranges for exploratory studies involving complex constructs, especially when supported by strong performance in RMSEA and SRMR. After removing the smoking variable, the revised model showed significant enhancements in fit indices, reduced complexity, and improved alignment with the observed data, thereby supporting its acceptability for this study.

Cronbach's alpha values for internal consistency reliability, both types of composite reliability, and AVE values can be found in Table 3, confirming that the scale measured the constructs with sufficient precision and that the constructs were well-represented by their respective indicators.

Table 3 Results of Reliability and AVE

	Cronbach's alpha	Composite reliability (rho_a)	Composite reliability (rho_c)	AVE
Job-Related	0.731	0.717	0.776	0.533
Psychological	0.772	0.865	0.709	0.769
Work Environment	0.635	0.748	0.739	0.583
Behavioral/Habital	0.819	0.802	0.700	0.546
Individual	0.696	0.892	0.774	0.569
WRMSDs	0.738	0.753	0.806	0.599

Notes, AVE: Average Variance Extracted, WRMSDs: Work-Related Musculoskeletal Disorders.

The Fornell-Larcker criterion values in Table 4 indicate strong discriminant validity for all the constructs in the model. In other words, each construct has been measured independently, with no significant overlap with other constructs, thereby enhancing the model's validity.

Table 4. Fornell-Larcker criterion

	Job-Related	WRMSDs	Work Environment	Behavioral/Habital	Individual	Psychological
Job-Related	0.730					
WRMSDs	-0.061	0.773				
Work Environment	-0.071	0.069	0.763			
Behavioral/Habital	0.083	-0.245	0.105	0.739		
Individual	0.063	0.225	-0.021	-0.090	0.753	
Psychological	-0.096	0.315	-0.132	-0.209	0.119	0.877

Notes, WRMSDs: Work-Related Musculoskeletal Disorders.

Figure 3 presents the fitted model, displaying the path coefficients and their corresponding (P-values). The results indicate that job-related factors have no significant effect on either WRMSDs or psychological factors ($P > 0.05$). On the other hand, work environment factors have a positive effect on WRMSDs and a significant negative effect on psychological factors ($P < 0.05$). Additionally, behavioral/habital factors have a significant negative impact on both WRMSDs and psychological factors ($P < 0.05$).

et al., 2021; Li et al., 2021; Russo et al., 2020), work experience (Jensen et al., 2002; Li et al., 2021), physical activity (Lee et al., 2023; Shahbazi et al., 2020), sleep quantity (Darvishi et al., 2024; Grier et al., 2020), psychological factors (Jensen et al., 2002; Li et al., 2021; Russo et al., 2020), job demand (Fan et al., 2024; Jensen et al., 2002; Kar et al., 2023b), and noise (Fan et al., 2024). In addition, the workstation design was significantly related to WRMSDs. A previous study reported similar outcomes (Haile et al., 2012). Workstation design significantly affects working posture, which in turn contributes to the development of WRMSDs (Lu & Aghazadeh, 1996). Furthermore, the physical workspace can influence productivity by as much as 20% (Leaman & Bordass, 1999).

By employing SEM, the direct and indirect effects of five independent latent variables (job-related, behavioral/habitual, work environmental, psychological, and individual factors) on WRMSDs, as well as the mediating role of psychological factors, were assessed. The results showed that workplace environmental factors have a significant direct impact on WRMSDs, consistent with previous studies (Bertin et al., 2020; Magnavita et al., 2011; Mirzaei et al., 2024). Notably, our study also found that environmental factors such as noise, chemicals, and vibration can significantly impact mental health, contributing to issues like anxiety, depression, and stress, in line with past studies (Kwon et al., 2021; Tota et al., 2024), then exert a significant indirect negative effect on WRMSDs through psychological factors. This supports the notion that unhealthy work environments not only impact physical health directly but also exacerbate psychological problems, which in turn influence musculoskeletal health.

Behavioral and habitual factors, such as sleep quantity and physical inactivity, were found to have significant negative impacts on both WRMSDs and psychological factors. These findings align with (Sugano et al., 2022). Psychological factors exhibited a significant positive impact on WRMSDs and played a mediating role in the relationship between workplace environmental and behavioral factors with WRMSDs. This finding underscores the importance of addressing psychological stress and mental health in workplace interventions, as supported by (Russo et al., 2020) and (Nascimento et al., 2024). Individual factors, including age, education level, marital status, and work experience, were significantly associated with WRMSDs, corroborating findings from studies by (Nascimento et al., 2024) and (Kar et al., 2023b). However, they had no indirect effects on WRMSDs through psychological factors as mediator. Finally, job-related factors such as workstation design, shift working, and job demands showed limited direct influence on WRMSDs in our study. This differs slightly from the past works (Kar et al., 2023b; Talapatra et al., 2024). Its indirect effect was also not significant. This discrepancy underscores the variability in how job-related factors impact WRMSDs across different studies and populations, suggesting that other mediating variables or contextual factors might play a more substantial role in your specific study environment.

In addition, the study's population, diversity in studied industries, and observed and latent factors combined to construct the models should be considered when discussing differences in findings. While the present study put environmental factors in a category separated from job-related ones, another study put both in one category (Kar et al., 2023b). The other one constructs a simple model in addition to considering just one category for environmental and job-related factors (Talapatra et al., 2024).

5.1. Occupational Applications

This study identified the major individual and occupational risk factors contributing to the occurrence of WRMSDs among workers in various production companies. The key findings indicate that mental issues, environmental factors, and poor workstation design substantially affect WRMSDs. These findings highlight the importance of developing ergonomic interventions and training programs tailored to the specific challenges faced by workers in these industries. A multidisciplinary approach involving ergonomists (for workplace design), occupational safety professionals (for environmental assessments), and mental health specialists (for psychological support) is essential to crafting comprehensive intervention strategies. This approach should encompass enhancing workplace design, promoting regular physical activity, and fostering healthy sleep habits. Routine assessments of the work environment are also crucial. Furthermore, targeted psychological support programs, such as stress management and mental health counseling, are vital components of occupational health strategies aimed at mitigating the mediating effects of psychological factors on WRMSDs. By adopting a holistic and integrated framework, companies can enhance employee health, comfort, and productivity, thereby creating a safer and more efficient workplace.

6. Conclusions

This study highlights the significant prevalence of WRMSDs among manufacturing employees. Potential risk factors influencing WRMSDs were identified. It was found that upper and lower limb disorders are multifactorial and complex, with workplace environmental, behavioral, and psychological factors as key contributors. This research shows how psychological factors play a big role in connecting mental and physical health in the workplace. By understanding this connection, we can better understand the complex relationship between minds and bodies at work. The results suggest that targeted workplace improvements, health promotion programs, and psychological support initiatives can collectively help to control WRMSDs.

The present study used a cross-sectional design to gather data, which may result in an underestimation of the true prevalence of WRMSDs. Since the WRMSDs prevalence was based on self-reporting, this could have led to a recall bias. Although the data were collected from different types of companies, it was limited to a single province, and the generalizability of the findings to others needs to be done carefully.

Future studies should focus on long-term studies to establish causal relationships between identified risk factors and WRMSDs. Additionally, investigating the ergonomic interventions' effectiveness and adjustments at both individual and organizational levels to reduce WRMSDs is crucial. Next studies can consider a wider range of manufacturing fields and worker populations to enhance generalizability

7. Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

8. Data Availability

All data generated or analysed during this study are included in the article. However, the data are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

9. Acknowledgments

This study was part of a PhD thesis project supported by Tehran University of Medical Sciences, Tehran, Iran (grant No: 1402-4-99-69404). In addition, the authors would like to thank all participants for their contributions to this study. Besides, the utilization of the Wordvice AI Proofreader to enhance the readability and language of the manuscript is declared by the authors. However, the authors checked and edited the content as necessary and accept full responsibility for the publication.

10. References

- Ahmadi, M., Zakerian, S. A., & Salmanzadeh, H. (2017). Prioritizing the ILO/IEA Ergonomic Checkpoints' measures; a study in an assembly and packaging industry. *International Journal of Industrial Ergonomics*, 59, 54–63. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ergon.2017.03.002>
- Asghari, A., Saed, F., & Dibajnia, P. (2008). Psychometric properties of the Depression Anxiety Stress Scales-21 (DASS-21) in a non-clinical Iranian sample. *Ijpb*, 2(2), 0–0.
- Babazadeh, T., Sarkhoshi, R., Bahadori, F., Moradi, F., Shariat, F., & Sherizadeh, yusef. (2016). Prevalence of depression, anxiety and stress disorders in elderly people residing in Khoy, Iran (2014-2015). *J Anal Res Clin Med*, 4(2), 122–128. <https://doi.org/10.15171/jarcm.2016.020>
- Belay, G. T., Woldegiorgis, B. H., & Prasetyo, Y. T. (2024). Structural equation modeling approach for the analysis of ergonomics risk factors and occupational injuries among building construction workers in Bahir Dar City-Ethiopia. *Heliyon*, 10(11), Article 11. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2024.e32234>
- Bertin, M., Nguyen, T.-H.-Y., Bonvallet, N., Bodin, J., & Roquelaure, Y. (2020). Occupational co-exposure to biomechanical factors and neurotoxic chemicals in a representative sample of French employees. *Journal of Occupational Health*, 62(1), e12090. <https://doi.org/10.1002/1348-9585.12090>
- Brett, J. M., & Drasgow, F. (Eds.). (2002). *The Psychology of Work: Theoretically Based Empirical Research* (0 ed.). *Psychology Press*. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781410602411>
- Bureau of Labor Statistics. (2016). *Nonfatal Occupational Injuries and Illnesses Requiring Days Away from Work, 2015*. Bureau of Labor Statistics. <https://www.bls.gov/news.release/osh2.nr0.htm>
- Choobineh, A., Daneshmandi, H., Saraj Zadeh Fard, S., & Tabatabaee, S. (2016). Prevalence of work-related musculoskeletal symptoms among Iranian workforce and job groups. *International Journal of Preventive Medicine*, 7(1), 130. <https://doi.org/10.4103/2008-7802.195851>
- Choobineh, A., Lahmi, M., Shahnava, H., Khani Jazani, R., & Hosseini, M. (2004). Musculoskeletal Symptoms as Related to Ergonomic Factors in Iranian Hand-Woven Carpet Industry and General Guidelines for Workstation Design. *International Journal of Occupational Safety and Ergonomics*, 10(2), 157–168. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10803548.2004.11076604>
- Christ, S. L., Lee, D. J., Lam, B. L., & Zheng, D. D. (2014). Structural Equation Modeling: A Framework for Ocular and Other Medical Sciences Research. *Ophthalmic Epidemiology*, 21(1), 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.3109/09286586.2013.867508>
- Cieza, A., Causey, K., Kamenov, K., Hanson, S. W., Chatterji, S., & Vos, T. (2020). Global estimates of the need for rehabilitation based on the Global Burden of Disease study 2019: A systematic analysis for the Global Burden of Disease Study 2019. *The Lancet*, 396(10267), 2006–2017. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(20\)32340-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(20)32340-0)

- Darvishi, E., Osmani, H., Aghaei, A., & Moloud, E. A. (2024). Hidden risk factors and the mediating role of sleep in work-related musculoskeletal discomforts. *BMC Musculoskeletal Disorders*, 25(1), 256. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12891-024-07387-0>
- Dastranj, F., & Helali, F. (2015). *Ergonomic checkpoints, practical and easy-to-implement solutions for improving safety, health and working conditions* (Translated ILO book 2010) (1st ed.). Farhange Rasa.
- Demissie, B., Bayih, E. T., & Demmelash, A. A. (2024). A systematic review of work-related musculoskeletal disorders and risk factors among computer users. *Heliyon*, 10(3), e25075. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2024.e25075>
- Dong, Y., Jin, X., Wang, J., Maimaiti, N., He, L., Wang, F., Jin, X., Wang, S., Zhang, Z., Forsman, M., & Yang, L. (2021). Study on the Associations of Individual and Work-Related Factors with Low Back Pain among Manufacturing Workers Based on Logistic Regression and Structural Equation Model. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 18(4), 1525. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph18041525>
- Environmental and Occupational Health Center of Iran (EOHCI). (2021). *Occupational Exposure Limit (OEL)*. Ministry of Health and Medical Education.
- European Agency for Safety and Health at Work., IKEI., & Panteia. (2019). *Work-related musculoskeletal disorders: Prevalence, costs and demographics in the EU*. Publications Office. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2802/66947>
- Fan, J., Tan, X., Smith, A. P., & Wang, J. (2024). Work-related musculoskeletal disorders, fatigue and stress among gas station workers in China: A cross-sectional study. *BMJ Open*, 14(7), e081853. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2023-081853>
- Grier, T., Dinkeloo, E., Reynolds, M., & Jones, B. H. (2020). Sleep duration and musculoskeletal injury incidence in physically active men and women: A study of U.S. Army Special Operation Forces soldiers. *Sleep Health*, 6(3), 344–349. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sleh.2020.01.004>
- Haile, E. L., Taye, B., & Hussen, F. (2012). Ergonomic Workstations and Work-Related Musculoskeletal Disorders in the Clinical Laboratory. *Laboratory Medicine*, 43(suppl 2), e11–e19. <https://doi.org/10.1309/LM7BQ15TTQFBXIS>
- Hair, J. F. (Ed.). (2010). *Multivariate data analysis* (7. ed). Pearson Prentice Hall.
- Hair, J. F., Hult, G. T. M., Ringle, C. M., Sarstedt, M., Danks, N. P., & Ray, S. (2021). *Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) Using R: A Workbook*. Springer International Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-80519-7>
- Jensen, C., Ryholt, C. U., Burr, H., Villadsen, E., & Christensen, H. (2002). Work-related psychosocial, physical and individual factors associated with musculoskeletal symptoms in computer users. *Work & Stress*, 16(2), Article 2. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02678370210140658>
- Jöreskog, K. G., & Soerbom, D. (1996). *Lisrel 8: User's Reference Guide*. Scientific Software International.
- Kakemam, E., Navvabi, E., Albelbeisi, A. H., Saeedikia, F., Rouhi, A., & Majidi, S. (2022). Psychometric properties of the Persian version of Depression Anxiety Stress Scale-21 Items (DASS-21) in a sample of health professionals: A cross-sectional study. *BMC Health Services Research*, 22(1), 111. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12913-022-07514-4>
- Kar, M. B., Aruna, M., & Kunar, B. M. (2023a). Risk factors associated with work-related musculoskeletal disorders among dumper operators: A machine learning approach. *Clinical Epidemiology and Global Health*, 24, 101438. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cegh.2023.101438>

- Kar, M. B., Aruna, M., & Kunar, B. M. (2023b). Structural equation modelling of work related musculoskeletal disorders among dumper operators. *Scientific Reports*, 13(1), 14055. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-40507-9>
- Katirae, N., Calzavara, M., Finco, S., Battini, D., & Battaia, O. (2021). Consideration of workers' differences in production systems modelling and design: State of the art and directions for future research. *International Journal of Production Research*, 59(11), 3237–3268. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00207543.2021.1884766>
- Krejcie, R. V., & Morgan, D. W. (1970). Determining Sample Size for Research Activities. *Educational and Psychological Measurement*, 30(3), 607–610. <https://doi.org/10.1177/001316447003000308>
- Krishnan, K. S., Raju, G., & Shawkataly, O. (2021). Prevalence of Work-Related Musculoskeletal Disorders: Psychological and Physical Risk Factors. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 18(17), Article 17. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph18179361>
- Kuorinka, I., Jonsson, B., Kilbom, A., Vinterberg, H., Biering-Sørensen, F., Andersson, G., & Jørgensen, K. (1987). Standardised Nordic questionnaires for the analysis of musculoskeletal symptoms. *Applied Ergonomics*, 18(3), 233–237. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0003-6870\(87\)90010-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/0003-6870(87)90010-X)
- Kwon, D., Kwak, K., Baek, K., Chi, Y., Na, S., & Park, J.-T. (2021). Association between physical hazardous agent exposure and mental health in the Korean working population: The 5th Korean Working Conditions Survey. *Annals of Occupational and Environmental Medicine*, 33(1), e33. <https://doi.org/10.35371/aoem.2021.33.e33>
- Leaman, A., & Bordass, B. (1999). Productivity in buildings: The 'killer' variables. *Building Research & Information*, 27(1), 4–19. <https://doi.org/10.1080/096132199369615>
- Lee, Y.-C., Hong, X., & Man, S. S. (2023). Prevalence and Associated Factors of Work-Related Musculoskeletal Disorders Symptoms among Construction Workers: A Cross-Sectional Study in South China. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 20(5), 4653. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph20054653>
- Leite, W. K. D. S., Araújo, A. J. D. S., Norte Da Silva, J. M., Gontijo, L. A., Vieira, E. M. D. A., Lopes De Souza, E., Colaço, G. A., & Bueno Da Silva, L. (2021). Risk factors for work-related musculoskeletal disorders among workers in the footwear industry: A cross-sectional study. *International Journal of Occupational Safety and Ergonomics*, 27(2), 393–409. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10803548.2019.1579966>
- Li, X., Yang, X., Sun, X., Xue, Q., Ma, X., & Liu, J. (2021). Associations of musculoskeletal disorders with occupational stress and mental health among coal miners in Xinjiang, China: A cross-sectional study. *BMC Public Health*, 21(1), Article 1. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-021-11379-3>
- Lu, H., & Aghazadeh, F. (1996). Risk Factors and their Interactions in VDT Workstation Systems. *Proceedings of the Human Factors and Ergonomics Society Annual Meeting*, 40(13), 637–641. <https://doi.org/10.1177/154193129604001312>
- Magnavita, N., Elovainio, M., De Nardis, I., Heponiemi, T., & Bergamaschi, A. (2011). Environmental discomfort and musculoskeletal disorders. *Occupational Medicine*, 61(3), 196–201. <https://doi.org/10.1093/occmed/kqr024>
- Marsh, H. W., Hau, K.-T., & Wen, Z. (2004). In Search of Golden Rules: Comment on Hypothesis-Testing Approaches to Setting Cutoff Values for Fit Indexes and Dangers in Overgeneralizing Hu and Bentler's (1999) Findings. *Structural Equation Modeling: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, 11(3), 320–341. https://doi.org/10.1207/s15328007sem1103_2
- Mirzaei, E., Kouhnavard, B., Daneshmandi, H., Seif, M., & Zamanian, Z. (2024). Determining the effect of environmental factors, work postures and mental workload on musculoskeletal

disorders in rescue workers and accidents of one of the water and sewage companies in Iran. *Work*, 78(4), 969–981. <https://doi.org/10.3233/WOR-220372>

- Nascimento, J. M. R. E. S., Bispo, L. G. M., & Silva, J. M. N. D. (2024). Risk factors for work-related musculoskeletal disorders among workers in Brazil: A structural equation model approach. *International Journal of Industrial Ergonomics*, 99, 103551. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ergon.2024.103551>
- Oakman, J., Clune, S., & Stuckey, R. (2019). *Work-related musculoskeletal disorders in Australia 2019: The latest research on work-related musculoskeletal disorders*. Safe Work Australia.
- Parno, A., Sayehmiri, K., Parno, M., Khandan, M., Poursadeghiyan, M., Maghsoudipour, M., & Ebrahimi, M. H. (2017). The prevalence of occupational musculoskeletal disorders in Iran: A meta-analysis study. *Work*, 58(2), 203–214. <https://doi.org/10.3233/WOR-172619>
- Ramdan, I. M., Duma, K., & Setyowati, D. L. (2019). Reliability and Validity Test of the Indonesian Version of the Nordic Musculoskeletal Questionnaire (NMQ) to Measure Musculoskeletal Disorders (MSD) in Traditional Women Weavers. *Global Medical & Health Communication (GMHC)*, 7(2). <https://doi.org/10.29313/gmhc.v7i2.4132>
- Russo, F., Di Tecco, C., Fontana, L., Adamo, G., Papale, A., Denaro, V., & Iavicoli, S. (2020). Prevalence of work related musculoskeletal disorders in Italian workers: Is there an underestimation of the related occupational risk factors? *BMC Musculoskeletal Disorders*, 21(1), 738. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12891-020-03742-z>
- Shahbazi, A., Mokhtarinia, H. R., Biglarian, A., & Gabel, C. P. (2020). The Prevalence of Musculoskeletal Symptoms in Iranian Spinner Workers in the Textile Industry and its Association With Demographic and Lifestyle Characteristics. *Iranian-Rehabilitation-Journal*, 18(4), 395–404. <https://doi.org/10.32598/irj.18.4.919.2>
- Soares, C. O., Pereira, B. F., Pereira Gomes, M. V., Marcondes, L. P., de Campos Gomes, F., & de Melo-Neto, J. S. (2019). Preventive factors against work-related musculoskeletal disorders: Narrative review. *Revista Brasileira de Medicina do Trabalho: Publicacao Oficial Da Associacao Nacional de Medicina Do Trabalho-ANAMT*, 17(3), 415–430. <https://doi.org/10.5327/Z1679443520190360>
- Sugano, R., Ikegami, K., Eguchi, H., Tsuji, M., Tateishi, S., Nagata, T., Matsuda, S., Fujino, Y., & Ogami, A. (2022). A Cross-Sectional Study of the Relationship Between Exercise, Physical Activity, and Health-Related Quality of Life Among Japanese Workers. *Frontiers in Sports and Active Living*, 4, 809465. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fspor.2022.809465>
- Talapatra, S., Parvez, M. S., Saha, P., & Kibria, M. G. (2024). Assessing the impact of critical risk factors on the development of musculoskeletal disorders: A structural equation modelling approach. *Theoretical Issues in Ergonomics Science*, 25(3), Article 3. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1463922X.2023.2219297>
- Tota, M., Karska, J., Kowalski, S., Piątek, N., Pszczołowska, M., Mazur, K., & Piotrowski, P. (2024). Environmental pollution and extreme weather conditions: Insights into the effect on mental health. *Frontiers in Psychiatry*, 15, 1389051. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyt.2024.1389051>
- Tripathy, J. P., Thakur, J. S., Jeet, G., & Jain, S. (2018). Structural equation modeling to identify the risk factors of diabetes in the adult population of North India. *Tropical Medicine and Health*, 46(1), 23. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41182-018-0104-y>
- Yildiz, E., & Ülker, E. (2017). *Measuring the Effects of Brand Authenticity Dimensions on Word-Of-Mouth Marketing Via Brand Image Using Structural Equation Modeling*. Vol. 8(3), 121–130.